

EARTH SCIENCES

FILTRATION OF THE GRAVITATIONAL FIELD OF THE ABSHERON-BALKHAN AREA

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Abstract

The article considers the issue of filtering the gravity field using derivative and gradient methods, which are highly sensitive in identifying weak local anomalies, gravity gradient zones, marginal parts of structures, deep faults and disturbances. As is known, these anomalies also display density heterogeneities of rocks, which can be associated with oil and gas fields and other minerals. Recently, various modifications and formulas for calculating gradients and derivatives of different orientations have been developed, which emphasize various features of anomaly-forming geological structures. The article presents the results of filtration of the gravity field of the Absheron-Balkhan area by the above methods.

Keywords: filtering, gravity derivatives, gravity gradients, transformation, deconvolution, gravity field grids.

Introduction

As is known, new digital devices for more reliable measurements of the gravimetric field have been developed, which also provides more accurate transformation and filtering of the gravity field. There are various methods of transformation and filtering of gravity-magnetic anomalies, which differ from each other in the sensitivity of field separation. The most sensitive of them are the gradient methods and the higher derivative methods, which allow identifying small variations in gravity anomalies and linearly elongated gradient zones. These anomalies can be associated with fault and disturbance zones, as well as hydrocarbon accumulations and the presence of ore deposits. The Geophysics department of Azerbaijan State Oil and Industry University (ASOIU) has developed algorithms and programs for identifying such anomalies on a computer using the graphical and analytical capabilities of the world-famous Surfer program [2-6]. Transformation and filtering of gravity-magnetic fields by the derivative and gradient methods are widely used in the world to solve various subtle geological and geophysical problems [1,8].

Methods and results of filtration of the gravitational field of the Absheron-Balkhan area.

The observed gravity field is complex, as it reflects the gravitational influence of density heterogeneities of the sedimentary strata and the deep structure of the earth's crust. The task of transforming and filtering the original complex field is to separate this field into its constituent elements. Interpretation of these components makes it possible to solve the set geological problems. There are various methods of transforming and filtering potential fields: the method of averaging over

an area or over a profile, the Saksov-Nigard gradient method, the method of higher derivatives, methods of analytical continuation of fields and various filtering methods. Various methods of filtering fields are presented in the Surfer program by Golden Software, the capabilities of which we used to transform the gravity field of the Absheron-Balkhan area.

The Absheron-Balkhan zone is a large linear structure connecting the Absheron zone of uplifts with the western end of the Balkhan zone of uplifts. Its length is 480 km, width is 20-25 km and it consists of numerous brachyanticlines. The arches of these brachyanticlines are complicated by mud volcanoes and a dense network of faults that fade with depth. In the western part of the zone there are local structures of the Apsheron archipelago, which are characterized by significant uplift. The folds are oriented in the NW direction, are located in an echelon shape and have dimensions of (4-30) x (2-10) km. The angles of dip of the wings increase with depth from a few degrees to 20 degrees or more and have an asymmetric structure. The eastern part of the zone includes the Balkhan zone, where the folds (Cheleken, Kotur-Tepe, etc.) are larger in size (up to 30 km) and have a large amplitude (up to 3 km) with steep wings. The steepness of these folds increases with depth to 40-50 degrees. The folds are complicated by faults and mud volcanoes. The Apsheron-Balkhan uplift zone is the most promising area of the Caspian Sea in terms of oil and gas.

In the beginning, we constructed a map of the observed gravity field of the Apsheron-Balkhan uplift zone (Fig. 1) based on a priori data [7] using the Surfer graphic program.

Fig. 1. Map of the observed gravity field of the Absheron-Balkhan uplift zone (2D)

As can be seen, the area is characterized by a large minimum of gravity with an intensity of up to -130 mGal, has an isometric shape slightly elongated in the north-west direction. In the north-eastern part there is a less intense maximum of gravity with an intensity reaching 70 mGal. The figure below shows a map of the observed gravity field of the Absheron-Balkhan uplift zone area in a 3D version, which creates a spatial representation of the gravity field of the Absheron-Balkhan uplift zone (Fig. 2). To transform this field, a

grid was first created in the Surfer program menu, and then linear filtering was performed based on this grid using the Roberts Row Detector method (3x3). The Roberts Cross operator calculates the two-dimensional spatial gradient of the gravity field. In this way, it highlights areas of high spatial frequency, which often correspond to the edges of structures. The figure below shows the results of filtering using this method (Fig. 3). As can be seen, high positive

Fig. 2. Map of the observed gravity field of the Absheron-Balkhan uplift zone (3D)

Fig. 3. Map of the horizontal gradient of the Absheron-Balkhan gravity field in 2D in isolines with a measurement unit of 1E (Roberts Row Detectors (3x3) filter)

gradients (4E) of gravity are noted in the southern and northeastern parts of the area. The gradients are oriented mainly in the sublitudinal direction and are complicated by gradients of the northwestern direction. Negative gradients (-4.5 E) of gravity are noted in the western and eastern parts of the study area and are also complicated by gradients of the north-western direction. The rest of the area is characterized by low values of the horizontal gradient of gravity. Then, based on the original grid, the following was filtering was performed using the Roberts Column Detector (3x3) method. This filter calculates the horizontal gradient of gravity along the Y axis (north-south direction). Based on the calculation results, a map of the horizontal gradient in the north-south direction was constructed (Fig. 4). As

can be seen in the figure, the north-eastern part of the area is characterized by high negative gradients and these gradients have a northwest-southeast orientation. Positive gradients of gravity are noted in the north-eastern and southern parts of the area.

The next filter that was used is Prewitt Row Detector (3x3). It allows you to select the maximum horizontal gradients in the direction along the X axis. In essence, this operator calculates the maximum horizontal gradient of gravity depending on the angle of direction. The results of deconvolution using this method are presented below (Fig. 5). As can be seen in the figure, the

Fig. 4. Map of the gradients of the Absheron-Balkhan gravitational field in 2D in isolines with a measurement unit of 1E (Roberts Column Detectors (3x3) filter)

Fig. 5. Map of the maximum gradient of the Absheron-Balkhan gravitational field along the X axis in units of $1E$ (Prewitt Row Detektor (3x3))

positive maximum gradient reaches 20 E in the north-western part adjacent to the Apsheron trough. The maximum values of negative gradients are observed in the north-eastern part and reach -45 E. The zone of negative maximum gradients, as in the previous case, extends from the south-east to the north-west. The western part of the study area is characterized by low positive values of the horizontal gradient.

Let's consider the Prewitt Column Detektor (3x3) filter type. This filter is similar to the previous filter, but it allows you to calculate the maximum horizontal

gradient in the direction along the Y axis. The results of the convolution of the gravity field of the study area using this filter are shown below (Fig. 6). As you can see, the maximum positive values of the gravity gradient are observed in the southern part of the study area, reach 20 E and have a sublatitudinal direction. In the northwestern part, a small section of the gradient with an intensity of +20 E is noted. The maximum values of negative gradients are recorded in the northeastern part of the study area. Their negative

Fig. 6. Map of the maximum gradient of the Absheron-Balkhan gravitational field along the Y axis in units of $1E$ (Prewitt Column Detektor (3x3))

values reach 35-40 E and they are also oriented in the north-west – south-east direction. Low gradient values mainly characterize the middle and northern parts of the studied area of the gravitational field.

The next type of filter is Sobel Row Detektor (3x3). This filter is very similar to Prewitt edge detector. The difference between them is that the weight of the central coefficient in Sobel operator is 2. Although Prewitt masks are simpler to implement than Sobel

masks, the latter have better noise suppression characteristics. Below are the results of gravity field convolution by Sobel Row Detektor (3x3) in two directions along the X axis and along the Y axis (Fig. 7-8).

The FreiChen Row (3x3) edge detector is also a first-order operation, like the previously discussed operators. Detection of edges of local anomalies that are associated with the edge parts of geological structural formations using the FreiChen Row (3x3) filter is realized by displaying the intensity vector using

a linear transformation. Detection of edges of gradient zones is performed based on the angle between the intensity vector and its projection on the X, Y axes. Below are the results of processing by the FreiChen

Row (3x3) filter in two mutually perpendicular directions (Fig. 9-10). As can be seen, the gradient pattern is confirmed once again.

Fig. 7. Sobel Row Detektor (3x3) gradient map of the Absheron-Balkhan gravitational field along the X axis in 1E units

Fig. 8. Sobel Column Detektor (3x3) gradient map of the Absheron-Balkhan gravitational field along the Y axis in 1E units of measurement

Fig. 9. FreiChen Row (3x3) gradient map of the Absheron-Balkhan gravitational field along the X axis in 1E units

Fig.10. FreiChen Row (3x3) gradient map of the Absheron-Balkhan gravitational field along the Y axis in 1E units

The results of deconvolution of the gravity field by the method of second derivatives of gravity are shown below (Fig. 11). As can be seen, the gradient zones are divided into smaller gravity gradients, the

interpretation of which is complicated by the small scale of the initial gravity field map. On the Roberts gradient slope angle map Row Detectors (3x3) of the Absheron-Balkhan gravitational

Fig.11. Map of the derivatives of the gradient of the Absheron-Balkhan gravitational field along the X axis in units of measurement 1E (Order 2 Derivative Filters)

field along the X axis the angles of inclination of the gravity gradients are marked in different colors in radian units (Fig. 12). As can be seen, the values of the

inclination angles vary within the range from +1.4 to -1.4 radians.

Fig.12. Map of gradient angles of Roberts Row Detectors (3x3) Absheron-Balkhan gravity field along the X axis in rad units

Conclusions:

1. A model of the Absheron-Balkhan gravity field of the Caspian Sea water area was constructed based on a priori data using the Surfer program in a modern interface. The area is characterized by a large minimum of gravity with an intensity of up to -130 mGal and a less intense maximum of gravity with an intensity reaching 70 mGal.

2. Based on the prepared grid of the gravity field of the Absheron-Balkhan zone, filtering was performed using the Roberts Row Detectors method along the X axis and Roberts Column Detectors along the Y axis. Gradient zones associated with the marginal parts, zones of disturbances and faults of geological structures were highlighted on the resulting map.

3. Filtering of the gravity field of the studied area was performed using the Prewitt Row and Column Detector (3x3), Prewitt Row and Column Detector (3x3), Sobel Row and Column Detector (3x3), FreiChen Row and Column Detector (3x3) methods, on which the positions of the gradient zones and marginal areas were clarified.

4. Using the "Math" function of the Surfer program, the resulting grid of the horizontal gradient of the Roberts Row Detectors field was transformed into a grid of the arctangent of the gradient of the original gravity field. Based on this grid, a map of the angles of inclination of the gravity gradient along the X axis was constructed, which are related to the angles of inclination of the studied structures.

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